

SAON-ROADS Glossary

Term	Definition
Advisory Panel (AP)	The coordinating and oversight body of Arctic ROADS that reviews Expert Panel progress, ensures alignment with Guiding Principles, and supports evaluation and integration across themes.
Arctic Observing Network (AON)	An international collaborative concept to create sustained, long-term observational networks in the Arctic. Its purpose is to coordinate and improve the collection, management, and use of data from various sources, including satellites, buoys, weather stations, and community-based monitoring, to better understand and respond to changes in the Arctic system. SAON is the international organization that facilitates the AON.
Arctic Observing Summit (AOS)	A biennial international forum co-led by SAON and IASC that brings together Arctic researchers, Indigenous experts, policymakers, funders, industry, regional and global organizations to improve coordination of Arctic observing and networking.
Arctic Roadmap for Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)	The collaborative, stepwise process under SAON designed to coordinate Arctic observing and data sharing based on achieving shared societal benefits under five guiding principles.
Benefit Assessment	A ROADS Phase II deliverable that transparently and clearly summarizes identified shared benefits of observing foci, detailing how shared benefits were assessed and prioritized for the purposes of implementing observing/monitoring activities, and who participated in the process.

BENEFIT Tool	The BENEFIT tool supports a specialized BENEFIT assessment method developed by the U.S. Arctic Observing Network (US AON). The name BENEFIT is an acronym that describes the main goals and features of this assessment process: B enefit E valuation N etwork E xploration B enefit A ssessments I mprove T ogether. It can be accessed at https://usaon.org/apps/benefit-tool/
CARE Principles	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics – framework for responsible data governance grounded in Indigenous rights and values. Developed in 2019 by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance.
Candidate Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs)	Proposed Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) identified by an Expert Panel during Phase III, reviewed through the ROADS Integrated Advisory Process for endorsement by SAON once widely agreed upon.
Champion	An Advisory Panel member assigned to an Expert Panel to help navigate the Integrated Advisory Process, broker connections, and facilitate feedback between the Expert Panel and SAON AP (and Board as needed).
Data Stewardship	Long-term, ethical management of data and knowledge, including documentation, storage, and access according to FAIR and CARE Principles.
Decision Log	A shared record of key choices and rationale maintained by the expert panel throughout the ROADS process for transparency and learning.
Expert Panel (EP)	A self-forming, collaborative group of Indigenous leaders, community representatives, scientists, and other partners that co-develops observing priorities and implementation strategies/plan around a specific theme, region, or issue based on shared societal benefits through the Arctic ROADS process.

Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)	A physical, chemical, or biological parameter of the Earth system prioritized for systematic observation because it is critical for understanding, monitoring, and predicting climate change and its impacts. ECVs are defined by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) to guide coordinated, sustained, and cost-effective climate observations worldwide.
Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)	A physical, chemical, or biological parameter of the ocean prioritized for systematic observation because it is critical for understanding, monitoring, and predicting ocean change and its impacts on climate, ecosystems, and society. EOVs are defined by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) to guide coordinated, sustained, and cost-effective ocean observations worldwide.
FAIR Principles	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable – guidelines for ensuring scientific data can be located and used effectively.
Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC)	An international ethical standard affirming that Indigenous Peoples must freely give informed consent before activities affecting their lands, knowledge, resources, lives and livelihoods prior to any activities being initiated. It ensures that consent is given voluntarily (Free), is sought well in advance of any activity (Prior), and is based on having received all relevant information (Informed). FPIC is a critical tool for upholding Indigenous Peoples' right to self-determination and participation in decision-making processes.
Foundational Engagement Step	The relationship-building period is meant to inform and prepare prospective EPs prior to formally engaging in the Integrated Advisory Process. It is designed to establish trust, purpose, initial partnerships, and to initiate engagement with the AP and Open Partnership meetings.

Global Climate Observing System (GCOS)	An international program that defines and promotes Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) for coordinated global observations.
Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)	A United Nations sponsored program supporting coordinated ocean observations and the definition of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).
Guiding Principles of Arctic ROADS	Five core principles identified to assure that the ROADS process are aligned with the goals of SAON and broadly-identified good practices for observing system development in an Arctic context.
Integrated Advisory Process (IAP)	The overall sequence of steps—Foundational engagement, Phases I–IV, and Evaluation—through which Expert Panels and the Advisory Panel co-develop, review, and refine observing plans and shared benefits.
International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF)	A framework developed by the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) initiative to systematically assess Arctic observing systems against user needs and agreed criteria. It supports identification of gaps, overlaps, and priorities to strengthen coordination, sustainability, and effectiveness of Arctic observations.
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	A non-governmental organization facilitating international scientific cooperation in the Arctic; co-leads Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks with the Arctic Council.
Indigenous Knowledge(s) (IK)	There is no single definition of IK; Indigenous Knowledge Holders are the only people who can truly define what IK is for their communities. For Arctic ROADS, we understand IK as complex, holistic knowledge systems based on Indigenous worldviews that are developed by Indigenous Peoples through deep intergenerational relationships with Arctic environments. IK systems are considered equally valid systems as are academic scientific systems in the ROADS process. IK is central to co-production and decision-making within Arctic ROADS. IK is not held by non-Indigenous people.

Indigenous Peoples	A group of people who share descendancy with the original inhabitants of a region before colonization and have historical continuity with pre-colonial societies. The group maintains distinct social, cultural, political, and economic characteristics, a strong link to their lands and waters, and their own unique languages, cultures, and belief systems. “Indigenous Peoples” should always be spelled out (never abbreviated) and capitalized, and should not be conflated with non-Indigenous local residents, Northern communities, or local communities.
Implementation Plan	A ROADS Phase IV deliverable clearly describing actions, partners, resources, data governance, and review mechanisms to put SAV observations into practice to achieve shared benefits.
Open Partnership Meetings	Public forums where Expert Panels, the Advisory Panel, and partners share updates, improve processes, coordinate efforts, and review new proposals.
Permanent Participants	The six Indigenous Peoples’ organizations with a special relationship to Arctic Nations in the Arctic Council:
Phase I – Initiate an Expert Panel	Timeframe within the Integrated Advisory Process where a group forms a focused, inclusive Expert Panel with a clear scope, balance of knowledge, and commitment to the Guiding Principles. Deliverables: Phase I Proposal and confirmed Advisory Panel Champion.
Phase II – Societal Benefit Assessment	Timeframe within the Integrated Advisory Process where Expert Panels work to systematically identify how better observing can deliver real-world benefits. Deliverables: Benefits Report and list of priority phenomena linked to those benefits.
Phase III – Requirements	Timeframe within the Integrated Advisory Process where Expert Panels translate shared benefits into specific observing and data requirements — what to measure,

where, how often, and how accurately. Deliverables: Requirements Tables and draft implementation outline.

Phase IV – Implementation Strategies	Timeframe within the Integrated Advisory Process where Expert Panels design the plan for action: who will observe, how data will be governed and shared, and how funding and partnerships will be sustained. Deliverable: Final Implementation Plan.
Process Workbook	A practical companion to the ROADS Handbook providing templates, checklists, and examples for each step of the IAP. It is used in real time by Expert Panels to document decisions and track progress.
Requirements Tables	Phase III templates detailing observing and data needs (what, where, how often, accuracy, and responsibility).
Societal Benefits (in the ROADS context)	The positive outcomes derived from continuous, high-quality, scientifically sound observations of Arctic social, economic, and environmental systems. These benefits occur across specific domains—including environmental, economic, and social spheres—where services, operations, and research activities are carried out.
Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON)	A joint initiative of the Arctic Council and International Arctic Science Committee that coordinates Arctic observing and data systems internationally.
Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)	The United Nations global goals for sustainable development, referenced as an example of shared benefit-based collaboration.
Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs)	A parameter of the Arctic system prioritized for observation because it addresses shared information needs across multiple sectors, including science, operations, and/or Indigenous community decision-making. SAVs are identified through the Arctic ROADS

process to guide coordinated and sustained Arctic observing strategies. The documentation for an SAV includes descriptions of how observations are/would be used, the relevant societal benefits from those observations, and the observing and data/information requirements necessary to achieve those benefits.

Shared Societal Benefits

The tangible, widely shared outcomes that improved observing and data systems provide for Arctic communities, decision-makers, and global users.

Theme

An organizing concept in the ROADS process associated with the functional scope of an Expert Panel's efforts. Themes reflect broad areas of work toward improved observing and data sharing. They may concern a particular observable phenomena - like sea ice - or an issue of concern - like ocean plastics. Themes are considered broader than Shared Arctic Variables. The specifics are scoped by the Expert Panel to allow for focus and progress.

Use Cases

Information use cases are specific information use scenarios invoked in the ROADS processes to help Expert Panels design better observing and data systems.

U.S. Arctic Observing Network (US AON)

The United States Arctic Observing Network (US AON) is a government initiative that coordinates U.S. federal agencies, partners, and Indigenous communities to establish and maintain long-term observations of the rapidly changing Arctic environment. It works to improve integrated Arctic-wide observing and data management to support research, products, and public services related to climate change.